

Table S1. Univariate models and root mean square prediction error (RMSPE, % of observed mean) for enteric CH₄ (g/d), CO₂ (kg/d), water intake (Water_{in}, kg/d), milk yield (MY, kg/d), fecal DM (F_{DM}, kg/d), fecal nitrogen (F_N, g/d), fecal carbon (F_C, g/d), fecal water (F_w, kg/d), total urine (U_t, kg/d), urine nitrogen (U_N, g/d), urine carbon (U_C, g/d), VS (kg/d) and dVS (kg/d) of lactating cows (n = 1111).

Eq.	Selected model ¹	Model performance ²			
		RMSPE, %	RSR	MB, %	SB, %
(S1)	CH ₄ = -110.94 (13.62) + 17.64 (0.56) × DMI + 3.04 (0.41) × ADF + 25.79 (1.93) × mFat - 1.69 (0.22) × MY	16.6	0.54	0.39	3.5
(S2)	CO ₂ = 2.71 (0.99) + 0.39 (0.019) × DMI + 0.078 (0.034) × CP	7.5	0.38	0.36	4.9
(S3)	Water _{in} = -22.94 (9.00) + 2.71 (0.28) × DMI + 0.36 (0.11) × DM + 0.57 (0.12) × MY	42.9	0.92	0.53	2.2
(S4)	F _{DM} = 0.38 (0.019) × DMI - 0.084 (0.032) × CP + 0.048 (0.015) × ADF	10.3	0.32	0.016	0.11
(S5)	F _N = -57.88 (7.10) + 10.16 (0.21) × DMI + 1.78 (0.34) × CP + 2.49 (0.58) × Lignin	15.0	0.41	0.20	3.9
(S6)	F _C = 206.65 (130.23) + 173.90 (2.56) × DMI + 20.12 (2.35) × ADF - 46.33 (4.48) × CP + 40.46 (11.47) × mFat - 98.68 (22.09) × mPro	10.7	0.34	0.033	0.039
(S7)	F _w = -3.90 (2.62) + 2.06 (0.047) × DMI + 0.42 (0.037) × ADF - 0.37 (0.078) × CP - 0.062 × (0.020) DM - 0.0078 (0.0015) × DIM	14.6	0.39	0.035	1.6
(S8)	U _t = 0.66 (0.088) × DMI + 0.77 (0.14) × CP - 0.21 (0.038) × MY	46.3	0.91	0.28	3.8
(S9)	U _N = -256.12 (10.96) + 9.38 (0.38) × DMI + 16.08 (0.49) × CP + 0.080 (0.014) × BW - 2.26 (0.14) × MY	20.0	0.46	0.11	5.7
(S10)	U _C = -214.79 (29.80) + 8.53 (0.87) × DMI + 11.84 (1.29) × CP + 0.13 (0.033) × BW + 9.96 (2.76) × Lignin	35.6	0.83	0.57	0.26
(S11)	VS = -1.64 (0.93) + 0.41 (0.019) × OMI + 0.061 (0.016) × ADF	10.3	0.34	0.61	0.0048
(S12)	dVS = -1.23 (0.92) + 0.37 (0.020) × OMI + 0.026 (0.010) × NDF	11.4	0.37	0.56	0.13

¹Model parameters are reported as posterior means and standard deviation in parenthesis. DMI is in kg/d; CP, NDF, ADF and Lignin are in % of dietary DM; mFat = milk fat, %; mPro = milk protein, %; DM is % of as-fed diet; DIM = day in milk; BW is in kg; OMI = organic matter intake, kg/d.

²RMSPE = Root mean square prediction error, expressed as a percentage of observed mean; RSR = Ratio of RMSPE to observed standard deviation; MB = Mean bias, expressed as a percentage of MSPE; SB = Slope bias, expressed as a percentage of MSPE.

Table S2. Univariate models and root mean square prediction error (RMSPE, % of observed mean) for enteric CH₄ (g/d), CO₂ (kg/d), water intake (Water_{in}, kg/d), fecal DM (F_{DM}, kg/d), fecal nitrogen (F_N, g/d), fecal carbon (F_C, g/d), fecal water (F_w, kg/d), total urine (U_t, kg/d), urine nitrogen (U_N, g/d), urine carbon (U_C, g/d), VS (kg/d) and dVS (kg/d) of nonlactating cows (n = 591).

Eq.	Selected model ¹	Model performance ²			
		RMSPE, %	RSR	MB, %	SB, %
(S13)	CH ₄ = 47.95 (5.61) + 17.69 (0.49) × DMI – 2.66 (1.14) × EE	15.9	0.59	1.1	0.45
(S14)	CO ₂ = 2.84 (1.01) + 0.57 (0.058) × OMI	9.3	0.45	0.041	2.5
(S15)	Water _{in} = 7.51 (4.00) + 1.27 (0.32) × DMI + 0.99 (0.34) × Ash	60.8	1.0	0.86	1.1
(S16)	F _{DM} = 0.34 (0.054) × DMI + 0.023 (0.012) × NDF	15.0	0.35	2.3	0.17
(S17)	F _N = –24.85 (3.17) + 9.10 (0.17) × DMI + 1.00 (0.16) × CP	14.6	0.39	1.3	1.5
(S18)	F _C = –536.12 (30.95) + 151.43 (2.71) × DMI + 19.55 (0.86) × ADF	13.8	0.32	1.5	1.1
(S19)	F _w = –6.52 (1.20) + 1.58 (0.066) × DMI + 0.20 (0.020) × ADF	20.9	0.41	4.1	0.45
(S20)	U _t = 9.62 (2.41) – 0.16 (0.071) × ADF + 1.18 (0.23) × Ash	69.8	0.98	0.55	0.010
(S21)	U _N = –132.45 (9.43) + 12.17 (0.44) × DMI + 8.64 (0.42) × CP + 0.45 (0.11) × NDF	18.8	0.55	7.0	0.093
(S22)	U _C = 14.38 (1.56) × DMI + 4.16 (1.47) × Ash	48.1	0.93	0.042	0.13
(S23)	VS = 0.37 (0.060) × OMI + 0.041 (0.017) × ADF	15.3	0.39	0.41	1.6
(S24)	dVS = 0.32 (0.052) × DMI	18.7	0.48	1.3	0.14

¹Model parameters are reported as posterior means and standard deviation in parenthesis. DMI is in kg/d; CP, NDF, ADF, EE and Ash are in % of dietary DM; OMI = organic matter intake, kg/d.

²RMSPE = Root mean square prediction error, expressed as a percentage of observed mean; RSR = Ratio of RMSPE to observed standard deviation; MB = Mean bias, expressed as a percentage of MSPE; SB = Slope bias, expressed as a percentage of MSPE.

Table S3. Univariate models and root mean square prediction error (RMSPE, % of observed mean) for enteric CH₄ (g/d), CO₂ (kg/d), water intake (Water_{in}, kg/d), fecal DM (F_{DM}, kg/d), fecal nitrogen (F_N, g/d), fecal carbon (F_C, g/d), fecal water (F_w, kg/d), total urine (U_t, kg/d), urine nitrogen (U_N, g/d), urine carbon (U_C, g/d), VS (kg/d) and dVS (kg/d) of heifers (n = 414).

Eq.	Selected model ¹	Model performance ²			
		RMSPE, %	RSR	MB, %	SB, %
(S25)	CH ₄ = 16.70 (0.58) × DMI + 0.85 (0.12) × NDF	22.4	0.71	5.3	1.6
(S26)	CO ₂ = 0.61 (0.067) × OMI	34.5	1.5	94.3	0.20
(S27)	Water _{in} = 1.70 (0.24) × DMI + 0.096 (0.050) × DM + 1.19 (0.26) × Ash	88.8	1.2	36.0	2.0
(S28)	F _{DM} = 0.35 (0.066) × DMI	22.2	0.59	31.5	0.090
(S29)	F _N = -35.40 (15.10) + 9.38 (0.20) × DMI + 1.16 (0.18) × CP + 1.49 (0.25) × Lignin + 2.36 (0.45) × EE	18.4	0.47	0.044	5.4
(S30)	F _C = -374.05 (38.58) + 159.92 (2.60) × DMI + 12.13 (0.76) × ADF	14.3	0.37	0.20	3.0
(S31)	F _w = 1.38 (0.077) × DMI + 0.16 (0.027) × ADF - 0.093 (0.059) × CP	33.5	0.74	21.0	5.4
(S32)	U _t = 0.54 (0.11) × DMI + 1.26 (0.14) × Ash	45.7	0.87	9.3	2.5
(S33)	U _N = -69.71 (16.49) + 10.68 (0.44) × DMI + 5.31 (0.34) × CP	25.4	0.53	0.66	3.4
(S34)	U _C = 13.96 (1.93) × DMI	81.0	1.0	8.3	0.59
(S35)	VS = 0.37 (0.065) × DMI	22.8	0.59	4.5	0.044
(S36)	dVS = 0.35 (0.072) × OMI	22.9	0.59	6.6	0.0064

¹Model parameters are reported as posterior means and standard deviation in parenthesis. DMI is in kg/d; CP, NDF, ADF, EE and Ash are in % of dietary DM; OMI = organic matter intake, kg/d.

²RMSPE = Root mean square prediction error, expressed as a percentage of observed mean; RSR = Ratio of RMSPE to observed standard deviation; MB = Mean bias, expressed as a percentage of MSPE; SB = Slope bias, expressed as a percentage of MSPE.